

Integration of electrical energy storage in wave energy hardware-in-the-loop test rigs

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Abstract—This paper presents a design methodology for integrating an electrical energy storage unit into a hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) test rig for wave energy converters (WECs). Typically, the power production from WECs is characterised by pronounced fluctuations at low frequency and high peaks compared to the average. Wave energy test rigs should be able to reproduce these variations to impose realistic conditions to the device under test. Thus, the grid connection of the rig must be sized to cope with high peaks, and additional measures may be required to avoid disturbances on nearby loads and negative effects on voltage quality. The integration of electrical energy storage can smoothen power fluctuations and mitigate these drawbacks, while resulting in lower installation and operating costs. The design methodology indicates how to effectively size the storage unit and which technology to favour based on the type and duration of test campaigns. Numerical simulation results are presented for a dual HIL test rig and operational profiles of three different WEC technologies. For designs with energy storage lifetime shorter than the calendar life, sensitivity analyses indicate that the rig's annual utilisation rate and the level of accelerated testing have a significant effect on the storage energy requirements.

Index Terms—Wave energy, Hardware-in-the-loop, Test rigs, Energy storage.

I. INTRODUCTION

TESTING in controlled environments is essential for evaluating the behaviour, capabilities and limitations of wave energy converters (WECs). From the concept development to scale demonstrations, dry-rig testing and tank testing have been widely used in the technological progress of wave energy systems [1], since the early developments in the field [2], [3]. Commonly performed prior to the deployment of a WEC, dry-rig testing can be a parallel or complementary activity to wave tank experiments. A variety of tests can be performed to demonstrate and optimise the performance of power take-off (PTO) systems [4]–[7] as well as to characterise key components [8], [9]. In addition, rig testing can be conducted to evaluate alternative solutions for electrical machines [10], [11] assess the performance of control systems [12]–[15], validate numerical models [16], [17], and analyse fatigue [18].

The relevance of dry-rig testing to prove WEC technology and the possibility to build cost-effective test benches of different scales have encouraged the development of a variety of test rigs and laboratory facilities. On this basis, the design of wave energy test rigs has been the topic of several scientific publications. Such studies include the design of test

rigs for linear electrical machines [13], [19]–[22], gyroscopic WECs [16], air turbines in oscillating water column WECs [23], [24], hydraulic PTO systems [25], [26], and drivetrain subsystems connected to the grid [15], [27]. Furthermore, several works use hybrid hardware-in-the-loop (HIL) test rigs, which integrate parts of the real system to be tested with a numerical simulation model running in real-time [16], [28], [29]. HIL testing has been widely used in different engineering applications, e.g., in the automotive industry, railway systems and grid applications [30].

One of the challenges with wave energy harvesting is related to power fluctuations at low frequency (e.g. 50–200 mHz) caused by the intermittent nature of waves. Without any means of power smoothing, the power generated by a single WEC is generally characterised by instantaneous peaks of significantly higher amplitude than the average output power, posing challenges for the rating of electrical subsystems [31] and connection with the electricity grid. To smooth these fluctuations, multiple WECs can be arranged in array configurations and energy storage components such as hydraulic accumulators and/or electrical energy storage systems (ESSs) can be added. A wave energy test rig must be able to accurately reproduce the power variations of a single unit in order to impose realistic conditions to the device under test (DUT). Thus, the drive system and the corresponding power electronic conversion stages must be rated for supplying the instantaneous power peaks required for operating the test rig. However, if a power profile with large variations and high peak values is drawn directly from the grid connection, the fluctuations may reduce the local voltage quality and disturb nearby loads.

The integration of an energy storage unit into a wave energy test rig can drastically reduce the power fluctuations drawn from the grid. Furthermore, the storage unit enables a higher power rating of the test rig for a given power supply at the location, whilst avoiding significant additional costs with modification or reinforcement of the electrical installations and/ or grid connection at the test facility. However, the benefits of including ESSs in test rigs for WECs have not been widely exploited in the field. Even though many works have been dedicated to rig design, e.g., [19]–[27], the design of energy storage units for wave energy test rigs has not been addressed in the literature yet.

This paper presents a methodology for integrating an energy storage unit into a dual HIL testing platform [32] capable of emulating a wide range of WECs and different operating conditions. The methodology consists of initially assessing the expected test cycle profiles to identify the most suitable ESS

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Fig. 1. Schematic of the dual HIL platform illustrating the structural components and drivetrain test rigs.

technologies for the application, and subsequently, thoroughly assessing the minimum capacity to be installed by accounting for the expected ESS degradation and lifetime, type of tests to be performed, and annual utilisation of the rig. Numerical analysis using operational profiles of different WEC technologies are presented, namely a dual-body point absorber (DBPA), an oscillating wave surge converter (OWSC), and a submerged pressure differential (SPD).

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. Section II presents an overview of the wave energy test rig used as the reference case study for energy storage unit integration. Section III introduces the methodology for designing the storage unit, which includes a preliminary design with general requirements and a thorough procedure to analyse the minimum capacity requirements following considerations on ESS degradation, ESS lifetime and annual utilisation of the rigs. By assuming different scenarios for the test cycle profiles, Section IV presents numerical simulation results for the ESS design. Conclusions are presented in Section V.

II. DUAL HIL TESTING PLATFORM

An innovative dual HIL platform is assumed as the reference case for illustrating the advantages of embedded electrical storage and the methodology for choosing storage technology and capacity. The main concept behind the HIL platform is to create a modular and flexible platform targeting characterisation, accelerated and destructive tests for a wide range of WECs and their subsystems. This section presents an overview of the platform and its design procedure including the scenarios that defined the loading envelopes, and specifications for the design of the drivetrain test rig, where the storage unit is integrated.

A. Main elements

The dual HIL testing platform aims at identifying weaknesses in an early design phase of WECs and performing qualification tests prior the deployment of a prototype in real ocean environment. This will be facilitated by running different tests on critical subsystems and components within a WEC, namely, characterisation tests for identifying key performances of selected equipment, accelerated tests for assessing qualitative and quantitative reliability features, and ultimate load testing for survivability purposes [32].

The platform represents the entire energy conversion process of a WEC, from the incident waves to the power delivered to an electricity grid. In contrast to a conventional HIL approach, where there is a single DUT at time, the dual HIL combines two equipped rigs where two subsystems can be tested at the same time. For instance, the platform can run tests involving both the PTO and mooring systems to anticipate possible failures resulting from the interaction among components, and evaluate the effect on the electrical variables. The main elements of the platform are the real-time simulator, the drivetrain test rig and the structural components test rig, as illustrated in Fig. 1. The real-time simulator consists of grid data and numerical models representing the incident waves, WEC hydrodynamics, and dynamics of PTO subsystems. The drivetrain rig replicates the WEC motion at the PTO input shaft and provides grid-compliant power, while the structural rig recreates the mechanical stresses caused by the ocean environment.

B. Design procedure

The flexibility of each rig is a fundamental aspect in the design process to allow for a range of possible DUT

Fig. 2. Block diagram of the drivetrain test rig in a standard configuration.

configurations and complementarity of subsystems that can be integrated within a WEC. Each rig must be capable of addressing HIL and accelerated tests individually, as they can also be used as single testing platforms. Thus, the design procedure followed five main steps, focusing on [32]:

- 1) *Load database*: To identify requirements for enabling the emulation of a wide range WECs and their subsystems. Three different device types and deployment sites were modelled/ simulated for several scenarios of power production, occurrence of fault, and parked conditions.
- 2) *Physical constraints*: To evaluate available mechanical and electrical systems/ parameters comprising the rigs and to identify the physical constraints.
- 3) *System layout and components*: To define the optimal layout, key components and setup of the overall platform.
- 4) *Software development*: To design basic numerical models for hybrid HIL tests and control strategies.
- 5) *Signal processing*: To ensure suitable time steps for running the numerical simulation model in dual HIL tests.

C. Specifications for the design of the drivetrain test rig

Following steps 1-3, the design procedure indicates that the ratings of the drivetrain rig exceeds the maximum power that can be absorbed from the local grid where the facility is located. Thus, an energy storage unit should be integrated into the design to provide the eventual exceeding power difference. The drivetrain rig is reconfigurable and adapted to linear or rotary PTOs, depending on the DUT. Considering the adaptability characteristics of the rig, electrical layout and available space at the facility, an electrical ESS is chosen as the most suitable option.

Fig. 2 shows the block diagram of the drivetrain rig, considering a standard configuration with a PTO system, a motor-side converter and a grid-side converter. The rig includes control software and hardware, as well as all required components up to the grid interface. A mechanical actuation system integrates the electrical machines powered by a supply unit and dc/ac converters. The electrical ESS is assumed to be connected at the dc link. The electrical actuation system consists of a variable input, fixed output transformer connected to a grid emulator, which replicates characteristics of strong and weak grids and different grid events (e.g., under- and over-voltage

TABLE I
POWER LIMITS AND EFFICIENCIES OF ACTUATION SYSTEMS.

Parameter	Value	Unit
Maximum peak power at motor inputs ($P_{m.max}$)	250	kW
Maximum continuous power at WEC input axis	100	kW
Maximum power from the grid ($P_{g.max}$)	70	kW
Efficiency mechanical actuation system (η_m)	0.68	–
Efficiency electrical actuation system (η_e)	0.74	–

ride through, connection and disconnection, emergency shutdown). Both actuation systems are governed by a rig controller, where actuation inputs are defined by a numerical simulation embedding a WEC model (and eventually a grid model) running in real-time.

Table I indicates the power limits and efficiencies of the mechanical and electrical actuation systems in the drivetrain test rig. The efficiencies of the mechanical and electrical actuation systems consider the reference efficiencies of components used in the rig (Fig. 2), as indicated in their data-sheets. For instance, the efficiency of the mechanical actuation system includes the efficiencies from the transformer to the torque sensor, while for the electrical actuation system, the efficiencies of the grid-side converter, transformer and grid emulator are included. More details of the efficiency values for each one of these devices are available in [32]. Following Table I, the maximum electrical power that would be required from the grid is 368 kW. However, the maximum power available from the external grid is 70 kW. Thus, the test rig should integrate an ESS for the cases when the required power exceeds the limit from the grid.

D. Scenarios for the loading profiles

A WEC model database was conceptualised to characterise the parameters of different WEC types and a broad range of requirements for various technologies. In order to obtain specific information for different WEC types, publicly available information was reviewed and three WEC models were selected [32]: a dual-body point absorber, an oscillating wave surge converter, and a submerged pressure differential. The numerical models of the WECs were conceptualised and implemented in WEC-Sim [33], a state-of-the-art tool for simulation of WECs. The PTO parameters of each WEC are

TABLE II
BASELINE WEC MODELS.

WEC type	Similar to	Description	Location	Deployment depth	Reference
DBPA	PowerBuoy (Ocean Power Technologies)	Two-body, self-referenced, floating point absorber type WEC. The design consists of a spar buoy moving up and down and connected to a subsurface reaction plate. The RM3 model in [34] assumes an hydraulic PTO located within the spar.	Surface	Target for water depths between 40 m to 100 m	Reference model project, RM3 [34]
SPD	CETO 3 (Carnegie Clean Energy)	Bottom-referenced WEC consisting of cylindrical buoy below the free surface. The buoy is connected via a wire to the PTO machinery on the seabed. The PTO has a hydraulic system, pumping seawater and sending it to the shore.	Submerged	Target for water depth of 20 but may be deployed in a variety of depths	NumWEC project [35], [36]
OWSC	Oyster (Aquamarine Power)	Bottom-referenced WEC, consisting of a pitching flap at the seabed. The PTO consists of a hydroelectric machinery system, pumping hydraulic oil to a station on the shore.	Seabed mounted & surface piercing	Targeted for shallow and intermediate water depths	NumWEC project [35], [36]

TABLE III
SCENARIOS FOR ASSESSING THE LOADING AND KINEMATIC CONDITIONS.

Type of sea state	Design situation	Specifications associated with
Normal	Power production	Normal operation (for performance-related tests)
Normal	Power production	Fatigue limit states (for reliability-related tests)
Extreme	Power production with sudden fault	Ultimate limit states (for survivability-related tests)
Extreme	Parked conditions (PTO as a break)	Ultimate limit states (for survivability-related tests)

optimised to improve wave power absorption, including PTO force constraints. An overview of the WEC types selected is provided in Table II. The main sources of information for the baseline WEC models were: (i) the Reference Model project [34], and (ii) the NumWEC Project [35], [36].

The loading profiles were identified by numerical simulations including several operating conditions and three deployment sites, namely, France, Spain, and Norway. The resulting load database was integrated with information from WEC developers, to create more comprehensive specifications [32]. The loading and kinematic conditions were assessed for normal and extreme sea states in different design situations. Normal sea states are represented by irregular waves following the JONSWAP spectral shape with significant wave height (H_s) and peak period (T_p) ranging from 0.25 to 5.75 m and 4 to 16 s, respectively. The obtained results informed the test platform specifications, as summarised in Table III.

III. SELECTION AND SIZING OF ENERGY STORAGE UNIT

The methodology for designing the energy storage unit consists of providing an initial assessment with general requirements for the unit and identifying the most suitable ESS technologies for the application. Subsequently, considerations on the ESS lifetime and practical usability limits of the rig are included to provide the minimum capacity to be installed. The estimation of the minimum capacity to be installed is determined by the ESS core technology and degradation model. As will be shown in the numerical analysis, the preliminary assessment indicates supercapacitors as the most appropriate technology for the test rig. Thus, the degradation model and the minimum capacity requirements (Sections III-C and III-D) are dedicated to energy storage units based on supercapacitors.

A. Problem statement

The aim is to integrate an energy storage unit to the drivetrain test rig of the dual HIL platform to compensate for the difference between the power rating of the rig (P_{max}) and the maximum power that can be absorbed from the electricity grid ($P_{g,max}$). The ESS will handle power flows of testing configurations where the input peak power is significantly higher than the average input/ output power. The design should consider the power and energy needs of the expected test cycles, type of tests to be performed, the expected usage of the rig and the desired ESS lifetime. Furthermore, it is assumed that the power generated by the rig during the tests (P_{rig}) is returned to the grid ($P_{rig,returned}$) for sizing the ESS.

B. Preliminary design

As a first step for dimensioning the ESS, power profiles from the baseline WEC models (Table II) are considered. The objective is to estimate the maximum power required from the storage device, and the maximum energy variation, to obtain an indication of type of storage technology needed. This step considers N power profiles obtained for a range of sea states. Prior to sizing the ESS, the WEC power is scaled down using the Froude scaling, for the cases when it is higher than the power from the test rig actuation system:

$$P_{rig} = P_{wec} \lambda^{3.5}, \quad t = t_{wec} \lambda^{0.5}, \quad (1)$$

$$\lambda = \begin{cases} (P_{max}/P_{wec,max})^{1/3.5}, & \text{if } P_{wec,max} > P_{max} \\ 1, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

and the power required from the grid P_{req} is

$$P_{req}(t) = P_{rig}/\eta_m(t) - P_{rig,returned}(t), \quad (3)$$

$$P_{rig,returned}(t) = \eta_{pto} \eta_e P_{rig}(t - \tau), \quad (4)$$

where P_{rig} is the power required by the test rig, $P_{rig,returned}$ is the power returned to the grid with a time delay τ , P_{wec} , t_{wec} are the power and time instant obtained from the WEC power profiles, respectively, λ is the scale factor, η_{pto} is the PTO efficiency, and $P_{wec,max}$ and P_{max} are the maximum power of the WEC, and the test rig actuation system, respectively. The scaling is intended to reduce the power within the test rig limits, and then, $\lambda \leq 1$. It should be noted that the scaling procedure is applied to accommodate a wide range of WECs, following the WEC database used for characterisation

of the test rigs. In a real-case test scenario, the rigs will be operating at full-scale whenever the power required by the DUT is lower than the maximum power of the rig. For the cases when scaling down is required, the associated loads will be reduced accordingly.

The maximum power and minimum usable energy that can be required from the ESS are used as a starting point for the ESS sizing. Then, an initial estimate for the ESS specifications is calculated by comparing the power required to emulate the WEC power profile (P_{req}) with the maximum power available in the grid ($P_{g,max}$). For the cases when P_{req} exceeds $P_{g,max}$, the required usable energy by the ESS is estimated as

$$E_{req,i} = \max \left(\int_0^T P_{ESS,i}(t) dt \right) - \min \left(\int_0^T P_{ESS,i}(t) dt \right), \quad (5)$$

where T is the total simulation time for the power profiles, $P_{ESS,i}$ is the power required by the ESS for the i^{th} profile, with $P_{ESS,i} > 0$ defined as discharge power, and SOC is the state of charge:

$$P_{ESS,i}(t) = \begin{cases} P_{req}(t) - P_{g,max}, & \text{if } P_{req}(t) \geq P_{g,max} \\ -P_{g,max} + P_{req}(t), & \text{if } SOC(t) < SOC_{max} \\ 0, & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

The required usable energy (E_{req}) is not a specification of the storage system size but a lower bound for its capacity. Indeed, practical considerations require oversizing, as will be described in Section III-D. Then, E_{req} is initially defined as:

$$E_{req} = \max(E_{req,1}, E_{req,1}, \dots, E_{req,N}). \quad (7)$$

In addition, the ratio (r_i) between the required usable energy and the maximum power is calculated. This is an important parameter commonly used for indicating the type of storage technology needed in a specific application.

C. Degradation model

The aging process in capacitor cells is mainly reflected in capacity loss and increment of internal resistance. In this work, the capacity degradation is the main criterion for the ESS end-of-life (EOL). Thus, the EOL criterion (k_{EOL}) is related to the capacity fade of capacitor cells/ module as [37]:

$$k_{EOL} = \left(1 - \frac{E_{EOL}}{E_{BOL}} \right), \quad (8)$$

where E_{BOL} is the ESS total energy capacity at beginning-of-life (BOL) and E_{EOL} is the remaining capacity at EOL. The estimation of the fractional capacity degradation depends on whether the ESS is in operation (charging/ discharging) or not. The phenomenon is known as calendar degradation (aging during storage) when the ESS is not in operation, and cycling degradation otherwise [37]. For supercapacitors, the voltage and cell temperature are the main factors affecting the capacity degradation rate. The following assumptions are considered:

(A1) As the EOL criteria is linked to the capacity fade, the degradation model only considers the effects on capacity fade given by calendar aging and cycling degradation.

(A2) Calendar aging occurs whenever the ESS is not cycled. The ESS is fully charged and the cells temperature follows the ambient temperature when the ESS is not in operation. Then, there is a constant capacity degradation rate during calendar aging.

(A3) When the ESS is in operation, the capacity degradation rate varies with the state of charge (voltage) and the cells temperature. Then, the average capacity degradation rate per cycle is determined by the cycling conditions (charge/ discharge power, depth of discharge and cell temperature rise).

From (A1)-(A3) and the principle of superposition, the total degradation ΔQ_{EDL} at the end-of-design-life (EDL) is

$$\Delta Q_{EDL} = \Delta Q_{cal} + \Delta Q_{cyc}, \quad (9)$$

where ΔQ_{cal} is the total calendar degradation,

$$\Delta Q_{cal} = \frac{Q_{L,cal}}{100} \frac{(365 - ADY)}{365} T_{EDL}. \quad (10)$$

$Q_{L,cal}$ is the capacity loss rate per year due to calendar aging (in percentage of initial capacity), ADY is the expected active days per year, T_{EDL} is the design lifetime in years, and ΔQ_{cyc} is the total cycling degradation at the EDL, which is estimated following the methodology described in [37]:

$$\Delta Q_{cyc} = \frac{T_{EDL}}{T_{FOP}} \sum_{k=1}^{N_{cycle}} D_{Qcyc(k)}. \quad (11)$$

The ESS is cycled N_{cycle} times at different conditions during the fundamental operating period T_{FOP} . In this work, the cycle life model based on fatigue theory reported in [38] in combination with the multi-factor cycle life prediction methodology reported in [39] are used for estimating the fractional cycling degradation per cycle D_{Qcyc} . This assumes that the impact of the operational factors on the ESS cycle life are nearly independent of each other, and the cycling degradation is uniformly distributed along the lifetime:

$$\Delta D_{Qcyc} = k_E \left(\frac{DoD}{DoD_{ref}} \right)^\beta \left(\frac{I_C}{I_{C,ref}} \right)^{\alpha_C} \left(\frac{I_D}{I_{D,ref}} \right)^{\alpha_D} e^{\gamma k_c}, \quad (12)$$

with

$$k_E = \frac{k_{EOL,ref}}{N_{CL,ref}} \quad \text{and} \quad k_c = \left(\frac{1}{T_{c,ref}} - \frac{1}{T_c} \right),$$

where DoD is the depth of discharge, T_c is the average cell/ module temperature, I_C and I_D are the charging and discharging currents/ C-rates, respectively, β , α_C , α_D and γ are degradation stress factor fitting parameters and $N_{CL,ref}$ is the number of cycles under reference conditions until the ESS reaches its reference EOL criteria ($k_{EOL,ref}$). The degradation in supercapacitors is mainly determined by the time they are kept at a given voltage and temperature [40]. This paper considers the degradation performance data reported in [41] along with the methodology reported in [42] for estimating the supercapacitor degradation stress factor parameters as: $\beta=2.86$, $\alpha_C=\alpha_D=-1$ and $\gamma=6976^\circ C$.

D. Minimum capacity requirements

This section provides an estimation of the ESS minimum capacity to be installed by considering the expected power cycles $P_{ESS,i}$ (as in Section III-B) and the ESS expected lifetime. In general, the ESS installed capacity will differ from the required usable energy due to three main factors [37], [42]:

- *Voltage range*: supercapacitors can operate between zero and the rated voltage. However, most electronics have a minimum voltage threshold for their effective voltage utilisation and usable energy. This works assumes that the operational voltage is kept within 50-100% of the rated voltage, and then, about 75% of the rated stored energy can be utilised. Furthermore, a dc-dc converter is included at the dc link of the test rig (Fig. 2) to make the voltage steadier.
- *Maximum power rating of the core technology*: The module/ cell of a supercapacitor has a maximum power to energy ratio limited by the maximum voltage and current rating, i.e. the peak and root mean square (RMS) values. The current limits are linked to the maximum allowed voltage variation over time (dV/dt) and the thermal performance of the selected capacitor technology, while the voltage varies with its state of charge. Then, higher current levels are required for the same power at lower SOCs, and vice versa.
- *Performance degradation and lifetime*: The supercapacitor lifetime is associated to its performance degradation: typically a decrease in the capacitance and an increase in the series resistance, both affecting the available/ usable energy. To be able to still supply the required usable energy by the application at EDL, the ESS installed capacity should account for the degradation.

Therefore, the ESS minimum capacity to be installed is determined by following the two steps described next.

Step 1. Calculation of the minimum required usable energy at EDL:

As described in the preliminary design stage (Section III-B), the minimum required energy for each power profile is estimated by (7). Using this as starting point, the minimum required usable energy at EDL is estimated by the following criteria:

- (1.a) The state of charge and the voltage range must be maintained within the defined design limits (the SOC varies 75% of the rated storage capacity at the EDL). Thus,

$$\Delta E_{M,EDL} = E_{req} \leq 0.75 E_{EDL}, \quad (13)$$

where $\Delta E_{M,EDL}$ and E_{EDL} are, respectively, the minimum required usable energy and the rated storage capacity at EDL.

- (1.b) The ESS peak and RMS power/ current should be at least as high as the required maximum peak and RMS power/current in the ESS load profile.

It is initially assumed that E_{EDL} is determined by the criterion

- (1.a). Then, the capacitor voltage (V_c) is estimated as

$$V_c(t) = \sqrt{0.75 V_R^2 \frac{E_c(t)}{\Delta E_{M,EDL}}}, \quad (14)$$

where

$$E_c(t) = \frac{\Delta E_{M,EDL}}{0.75} - \int_0^t P_{ESS,i}(\tau) d\tau. \quad (15)$$

The C-rates (I_c/AH) for the maximum peak and RMS currents can be estimated by the power and energy relations,

$$\frac{P_{ESS,i}(t)}{E_{EDL}} \simeq \frac{V_c(t) I_c(t)}{0.5 V_R AH}, \quad (16)$$

$$\frac{I_c(t)}{AH} \simeq \frac{\sqrt{3}}{4} \frac{P_{ESS,i}(t)}{\sqrt{\Delta E_{M,EDL} E_c}}, \quad (17)$$

where the equivalent capacity AH , is considered as the average current that can be supplied per hour until the rated energy storage is drained. Then, $\Delta E_{M,EDL}$ can be adjusted to fulfill the current rating of the considered capacitor technology.
Step 2. Estimation of the minimum energy required for the initial capacity:

The minimum energy required for the initial capacity to be installed (E_{BOL}) is estimated considering the minimum required usable energy at EDL while accounting for the performance degradation. For that, the following criteria are considered:

- (2.a) The energy cycling prescribed by the input load profile should not cause capacitor cells to reach their EOL before EDL. Then,

$$\Delta Q_{cal} + \Delta Q_{cyc} \leq k_{EOL} \cdot E_{BOL,1}. \quad (18)$$

- (2.b) The calendar capacity degradation alone should not reduce the storage capacity before EDL,

$$E_{BOL,2} - E_{EDL} \leq \frac{Q_{L,cal}}{100} T_{EDL}. \quad (19)$$

- (2.c) The cycling capacity degradation, and the calendar capacity degradation in non-used periods, should not reduce the remaining capacity at EDL,

$$E_{BOL,3} - E_{EDL} \leq \Delta Q_{cal} + \Delta Q_{cyc}. \quad (20)$$

Criteria (2.b) and (2.c) ensure the SOC does not go outside the design limits for the defined ESS load profile. Finally, the minimum capacity to be installed is given by the maximum of all calculated capacities, i.e.

$$E_{BOL} = \max(E_{BOL,1}, E_{BOL,2}, E_{BOL,3}). \quad (21)$$

E. Considerations on the practical usage of the rig and the ESS lifetime

The main aspects affecting the sizing of the storage unit are the expected power and energy flows during the tests, ESS degradation, duration of the tests and how often the tests are conducted in a year. Thus, considerations on practical usage of the drivetrain rig are included in the design to indicate how the type of the test and the expected usage of the rig will affect the ESS lifetime.

1) *Nature of the tests*: The drivetrain test rig is designed for addressing characterisation (e.g., mechanical friction, efficiency and grid compliance), accelerated endurance and HIL tests. Characterisation and HIL tests will mainly impact the power profiles and the duration of the tests. Such tests will assist in the identification of key performances of the equipment under test. For instance, it should be expected that sinusoidal profiles will be considered for characterisation of efficiency or friction and to verify if control strategies are properly implemented, while profiles obtained from irregular waves will be used to characterise grid connection or verify the performance of the overall system. In contrast, accelerated testing will assess reliability and require a modification on the time scale of the tests. Thus, a dedicated procedure is considered to verify how this type of test affect the ESS design.

Here, accelerated tests are specified by shortening the time duration of the simulation data while preserving the power information and the number of samples, as well as the annual utilisation of the rigs. For that, a test acceleration factor (k_{TAF}) is introduced to reduce the timestep of $P_{ESS,i}$. This assumes the acceleration increase will have a negligible effect on the overall power feeding the actuation system. The power data is preserved but with a shorter time duration, and then, the required cycled energy is lower than in the original data. As the power profiles are repeated more times in a year, the annual energy throughput is constant. However, it might be expected that there will be an increment in the ESS lifetime due to the decrease in the depth of discharge per cycle. This will be analysed in Section IV-D. Another possible implication of accelerated testing on the practical usage of the rigs can be related to an increase in the power demanded by inertial components of the drivetrain rig. As a portion of the power is used for accelerating and decelerating the components, the capability of the mechanical actuation system might be reduced depending on the degree of acceleration (defined by the acceleration factor k_{TAF}), kinematic profiles required by the tests, simultaneous load values and size of moving parts. However, this aspect is not considered for sizing the ESS.

2) *Annual usage of the test rig*: The influence of the annual usage of the rig on the ESS design can be determined by performing numerical sensitivity analyses that evaluate the ESS minimum required capacity at BOL (E_{BOL}) to meet the designed lifetime in years (T_{EDL}), and/ or estimate the ESS expected lifetime reduction for a given installed ESS capacity, for a range of planned annual utilisation of the rigs (in hours/year). This will be illustrated in Section IV-E.

IV. NUMERICAL ANALYSIS

This section presents the results obtained with the design of the integrated energy storage unit into the dual HIL platform. The results are based on numerical simulation studies with different power profiles and annual utilisation of the test rig.

A. Test cycle profiles

The power profiles used for sizing the energy storage unit were obtained under normal WEC operation targeting

TABLE IV
SCENARIOS FOR THE TEST CYCLE PROFILES.

Scenario	N	Power profile	WEC
A	156	Obtained from sea states with $H_s = [0.25:0.5:5.75]$ m, $T_p = [4:1:16]$ s $T = 30$ min	DBPA, OWSC, SPD
B	78	Obtained from sea states representative of the West coast of Norway $T = 30$ min	DBPA
C	1	Sinusoidal power profile, $125 + 125 \sin(2\pi t/5 - \pi/2)$ $T = 10$ s	DBPA

specifications for performance-related tests and reliability-related tests, i.e. the normal sea states as defined in Table III. Table IV summarises the scenarios for the power profiles. For all WECs, the power profiles in scenarios A and B were obtained by assuming PTO systems with a linear spring-damper model. The PTO parameters (damping and stiffness) were optimised for a set of sea state conditions to improve the mean absorbed power of the WECs. The DBPA optimum configuration consisted of a purely damping control, while for the SPD and OWSC, reactive control was used, i.e. both damping and stiffness were optimised [32]. To cover the full range of possibilities in terms of power requirements, a sinusoidal profile requiring the maximum peak power of the rig is included in the analysis, as indicated in Table IV. Furthermore, sinusoidal profiles are standard for characterising WECs in constant speed and to verify if PTO control strategies are correctly implemented.

The maximum power from the WECs exceeds 250 kW for some of the studied sea states. Therefore, to be able to accommodate a wide range of WECs, the power profiles are scaled down before sizing the energy storage device, following (1)-(2). This avoids capping the WEC power to the maximum available power of the test rig. Figure 3 shows the obtained scale factors for each one of the WECs in scenario A, where the dashed lines indicate the limits where $\lambda = 1$, i.e. scaling is not needed in the region to the left of the lines. It can be observed that the power is scaled down for the majority of sea states with H_s greater than 0.75 m, for the DBPA and OWSC, and greater than 1.25 m for the SPD.

B. Identification of core technology

Table V shows the minimum energy capacity required (in kWh), the maximum power (in kW), and the maximum and minimum ratio of energy and power (in seconds) obtained by following the preliminary design (Section III-B) for scenario A. The simulations consider the PTO system to be tested has an efficiency of 40% (worst case scenario) and 60% (best case scenario). Furthermore, a time delay of $\tau = 50$ ms is considered for the power returned to the grid.

A maximum energy level of about 0.3 kWh is required to emulate either the DBPA or the OWSC, while the SPD requires lower energy levels around 0.1 kWh. The maximum power required from the ESS is about 250 kW, and the ratio of energy and power ranges from 0.1 s to 5 s. Figure 4 illustrates the timeseries of power and energy required by the ESS

Fig. 3. Scaling factors (λ) for the WEC power profiles in scenario A.

TABLE V
ESS MINIMUM ENERGY CAPACITY [kWh], MAXIMUM POWER [kW], AND RATIOS OF ENERGY AND POWER [s] (PRELIMINARY DESIGN).

$\eta_{pto} = 0.40$				
WEC	E_{req}	$\max(P_{ESS,i})$	$\max(r_i)$	$\min(r_i)$
DBPA	0.30	225.57	4.86	0.36
OWSC	0.27	236.55	4.35	0.24
SPD	0.07	252.42	1.17	0.17
$\eta_{pto} = 0.60$				
WEC	E_{req}	$\max(P_{ESS,i})$	$\max(r_i)$	$\min(r_i)$
DBPA	0.22	188.31	4.20	0.64
OWSC	0.18	208.54	3.45	0.14
SPD	0.06	229.03	1.14	0.10

when performing the emulation of the DBPA for the sea state with maximum ratio of energy and power. Overall, the analysis of the time series indicates that the testing profiles are characterised by a sequence of power spikes with a relatively short duration and a high ratio between peak power and energy. This is confirmed by the ratio between energy and power that is in the range of a few seconds. Thus, the test rig requires mainly a support in terms of power with a relatively modest energy. This indicates that the most suitable storage technology is based on supercapacitors, which can be also verified by locating the energy and power requirements on a Ragone plot. An example of Ragone plot can be found in [43].

C. Minimum capacity requirements

The test cycle profiles and their expected occurrence per year are utilised for sizing the ESS. As a safety margin for the design, it is assumed that $\eta_{pto} = 0.40$ from now on. In addition, the minimum capacity is directly determined by the core technology of the ESS. This work considers supercapacitors' modules BMOD0006 (20.6Wh/160V) and BMD0008 (26.6Wh/160V) from Maxwell Technologies [44], herein referenced as module MA and MB, respectively. The performance parameters can be commonly found in the product data-sheet, except for the equivalent capacity (AH), which is used here as a reference parameter for the energy capacity assessment, and the degradation parameters as discussed in Sec. III-C. Note that module parameters are preferred for this assessment since they are derated when compared to cell parameters, due to the additional components in the module and the required cell balancing algorithm when many cells are connected in series.

Fig. 4. Timeseries of power and energy for DBPA case requiring maximum ratio: $r_i = 4.86$ s, $\lambda = 0.49$ (sea state: $H_s = 1.25$ m $T_p = 14$ s).

TABLE VI
ESS REQUIREMENTS FOR SCENARIOS B AND C.

Requirement	Scenario B	Scenario C
E_{req} [kWh]	0.26	0.24
(max) peak C-rate [1/h]	943.74	550.38
(max) RMS C-rate [1/h]	80.38	235.46
Peak charge power [kW]	70.5	71.68
Peak discharge power [kW]	224.5	224.2
(max) RMS power per energy cycle [kW]	65.94	107.95
(max) RMS power per power series [kW]	23.42	89.18

Initially, each power profile is characterised by its required energy, and maximum RMS and peak C rates. Table VI summarises the main ESS requirements. An ESS usable energy of about 0.26 kWh is required for scenario B, and about 0.24 kWh for scenario C that has a sinusoidal profile requiring the rig peak power every 5 seconds. While scenario C has the highest cycling and RMS power requirements, scenario B has the highest peak C-rates requirements.

Following steps 1-2 (Sec. III-D), the minimum capacity to be installed is estimated by using the parameters of the capacitor modules MA and MB. Fig. 5 shows the minimum capacity constraints versus design lifetime (T_{EDL}), while Fig. 6 shows

Fig. 5. Minimum capacity constraints versus design lifetime for (a) scenario B, and (b) scenario C.

Fig. 6. Required minimum installed energy at BOL and energy at EDL versus design lifetime for (a) scenario B, and (b) scenario C.

the required minimum E_{BOL} , and required E_{EDL} , versus T_{EDL} for both scenarios.

Fig. 5 shows the required E_{BOL} for the two supercapacitor modules, as described by criteria (2.a)-(2.c). The required E_{BOL} increases proportionally to T_{EDL} with the ESS sized to avoid EOL before EDL (solid lines), which is a stronger requirement than ensuring sufficient capacity at EDL, when it accounts for cycling and calendar and calendar (dashed-dotted lines) or only calendar aging (dashed lines). It can also be noted that for T_{EDL} beyond 10 years, the required E_{BOL} increases exponentially. This is due to the maximum calendar life of 12 years (at rated voltage) of the supercapacitor technology. Therefore, the EOL will be reached after around 12 years, regardless of the ESS usage.

In Fig. 6, the actual/ discrete E_{BOL} with 800 V rated voltage (5 modules in series per string and N_p strings in parallel) is included. For the same T_{EDL} , module MA (i.e. the module with the lowest energy content 20.6Wh/160V and the highest C rates) has the configurations with the lowest required E_{BOL} in both scenarios. This is because the required E_{EDL} is

TABLE VII
ESS CONFIGURATIONS TO ACHIEVE 800V RATED VOLTAGE AND BASED ON THE SUPERCAPACITOR MODULE 20.6Wh/160V ($N_s = 5$)

Configuration parameter	Scenario B		Scenario C	
E_{BOL} [kWh]	0.618	0.721	1.339	1.442
Initial rated capacitance [F]	6.96	8.12	15.08	16.24
N_p	6	7	13	14
max (I_p) [A]	1020	1190	2210	2380
max (I_c) [A], @ $\Delta T = 40^\circ\text{C}$	72	84	156	168
T_{EDL} [years]	5	9.8	6	8.2

Fig. 7. Required Energy at EDL and expected lifetime as a function of the test acceleration factor for scenario B (left) and scenario C (right).

mainly constrained by the required C-rates, which depend on the current rating. The ESS configurations based on module MA provide the best trade-off between installed capacity and expected ESS lifetime and are indicated in Table VII. The assessments in the following sections use these configurations.

D. Accelerated testing versus ESS lifetime

Fig. 7 shows the required energy as a function of the test acceleration factor (k_{ATF}), including E_{EDL} , E_{BOL} and expected lifetime, respectively to meet the design life and installing capacity in Table VII. It can be noted that $\Delta E_{M,EDL}$ and E_{EDL} decrease as the test acceleration factor increases. Therefore, the minimum required E_{BOL} to meet the design life also decreases. For each individual scenario, the required energy trend is similar for both ESS designs in Table VII. However, scenario C has higher decrement rate than B. On the other hand, when E_{BOL} is constant, the depth of discharge decreases with an increase in the acceleration factor. As the fractional degradation tends to be lower, the expected lifetime increases. For instance, an accelerated testing that divides the timestep of the original data by 2, increases the ESS expected lifetime by 22%, if $E_{BOL} = 0.72$ kWh, or 140%, if $E_{BOL} = 0.62$ kWh, when compared to tests without acceleration factor effects for scenario B. For scenario C, the ESS expected lifetime increases by 58% if $E_{BOL} = 0.144$ kWh, or 117% if $E_{BOL} = 1.34$ kWh. However, the influence on the lifetime becomes negligible if k_{ATF} is increased beyond 2, because the calendar aging becomes dominant.

Fig. 8. Required ESS installed capacity as a function of the desired ESS lifetime for different rig usage time in scenario B (left) and scenario C (right).

Fig. 9. Required Energy at EDL and expected lifetime versus rig usage time in scenario B (left) and scenario C (right).

E. Annual utilisation of the rig versus ESS lifetime

Fig. 8 shows a numerical sensitivity analysis of the actual/discrete E_{BOL} for a range of planned annual utilisation of the rig (in hours/year) for scenarios B and C. It can be seen that E_{BOL} increases with the planned usage time. An increase in the rig usage time by a factor of 5 in a year, will require an E_{BOL} about 9% higher in both scenarios. The impact of rig usage on ESS sizing becomes less significant for T_{EDL} beyond 10 years, as calendar degradation becomes dominant.

A second analysis is performed to evaluate the expected variation on the ESS lifetime for a range of annual utilisation of the rigs when E_{BOL} is constant. Fig. 9 shows E_{EDL} , E_{BOL} , and expected lifetime, respectively to meet design life and installed capacity in Table VII, versus the annual utilisation of the rig. It is shown that E_{BOL} increases as the utilisation of the rig increases. However, the actual/discrete E_{BOL} only increases when the rig usage increases by a factor of 2 and 3 in a year, respectively, for scenario B and C. The increment follows the installation of an additional string (5 series modules, around 0.1 kWh) to meet the string voltage constraint of 800 V. However, when E_{BOL} follows the same capacity as in Table VII, the expected lifetime decreases with the annual utilisation of the rigs. The ESS lifetime reduction depends on the proportion between calendar and cycling degradation, as both degradation components are a function of the rig usage. If the rigs are used five times more often, the ESS expected lifetime is reduced by about 4.1 and 4.5 years in scenarios B and C, respectively.

V. CONCLUSION

This study proposed a methodology to integrate an energy storage unit to wave energy HIL test rigs. As a case study, a testing platform designed for a wide range of wave energy systems was considered. Numerical analyses showed that the ESS support is characterised by a sequence of power spikes with relatively short duration and high ratios between peak power and energy, indicating supercapacitors as the most suitable technology for the application. The minimum capacity

to be installed was thoroughly analysed following the expected power profiles during the tests, ESS physical constraints and lifetime, as well as the annual utilisation of the rig.

The nature of the test characterises the expected power profiles and duration. When performing accelerated testing, the test duration is shortened but the power of the original data is preserved. Then, the required cycled energy is reduced. Such reduction in test duration has the most positive effect on the ESS lifetime for the cases when the ESS is designed to meet a lifetime shorter than the expected calendar lifetime, and the acceleration factor is lower than two. For instance, if the ESS is sized to achieve around 5-6 years lifetime (around half of the expected calendar life), the ESS expected lifetime will have an improvement of 100-140%, depending on the power profile to be tested. However, this positive effect on the lifetime becomes marginal when the ESS is sized to achieve a lifetime comparable to the reference calendar life or for acceleration factors greater than 2.

The expected duration of test campaigns has a significant impact on the required ESS installed capacity but only for ESS design lifetimes shorter than the expected reference calendar life at rated voltage. The impact is more significant for sinusoidal profiles requiring the peak power of the rig. On the other hand, for the same ESS installed capacity, the ESS expected lifetime decreases non-linearly with an increase in operation. For instance, the lifetime can reduce about 4 years if the rigs operate five times more in a year.

The numerical sensitivity analyses related to accelerated tests and the expected annual utilisation of the rigs are specifically developed for the context of rig testing. However, the general methodology for the energy storage design can be readily adapted to ESSs for wave energy converters.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This project has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under IMPACT grant agreement No 101007071.

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